

Upside-Down Magic Squares of Type $4k$, $6k$ and $12k$ Using the Digits 6 and 9

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The whole work is without use of any programming language.

Abstract

*This work brings **magic squares** of type $4k$, $6k$ and $12k$ only for two digits 6 and 9. Each magic square contains 12-digits in each cell. Just with two digits, one can have exactly 1024 different possibilities of 12-digits combinations from two digits. In case of $4k$, we have written **magic squares** of orders: 4, 8, ..., 60 and 64. In case $6k$, we have written **magic squares** of orders: 6, 12, ..., 54 and 60. In case of $12k$, we have written magic square of orders 6, 12, 24, 36, 48 and 60. All the blocks of **magic squares** of orders 4, 6 and 12 are of **equal sums** in each case. The same work for the digits 1 and 8 is done in Taneja [42], and for the digits 2 and 5 can be seen in Taneja [43]. The work on multiples of 3, 5, 7, etc. shall be dealt elsewhere. Later, the work shall be extended up to magic squares of order 128 having 14-digits in each cell just with two digits, either $\{1,8\}$, $\{2,5\}$ and $\{6,9\}$. In the first two cases the work is always **upside-down** and **mirror looking**, while in the third case for the digits 6 and 9, the work is only **upside-down**. When the **magic squares** are **upside-down** and **mirror looking**, we call them as **universal magic squares**. In this paper, all the results are **upside-down**. In case multiples of 4 and , the results are **pandiagonal**. The whole work is without use of any **programming language**. It is just based on the number's combinations.*

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The above groups are considered in such a way that they are with their **upside-down** numbers. Making possible combinations, these 5 groups, it lead us to 25 magic squares of order 12 with equal **magic sums** $S_{12 \times 12}^n := 999999999990$, $n = 1, 2, 3, 4$ and 5. These magic squares are given in Appendix 7, and are numbered according to following Table:

Table 1.3.

1	2	3	4	5
1=(1,1)	6=(1,2)	11=(1,3)	16=(1,4)	21=(1,5)
2=(2,1)	7=(2,2)	12=(2,3)	17=(2,4)	22=(2,5)
3=(3,1)	8=(3,2)	13=(3,3)	18=(3,4)	23=(3,5)
4=(4,1)	9=(4,2)	14=(4,3)	19=(4,4)	24=(4,5)
5=(5,1)	10=(5,2)	15=(5,3)	20=(5,4)	25=(5,5)

2 Upside-down Pandiagonal Magic Squares Multiples of 4

In Appendix 5 there are total 256 magic squares of order 4. All of them are **upside-down pandiagonal magic squares** with **magic sums** $S_{4 \times 4}^n := 155555555554$, $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 256$. Let's write a Table 1.1 in the following way:

Figure 2.1.

The following subsections lead us to **upside-down pandiagonal magic squares** multiples of 4, i.e., of orders 8, 12, 16, 20, 24, 28, 32, 36, 40, 44, 48, 52, 56, 60 and 64. These are chosen according to colors appearing in the table ??.

$1=(1,1)$	$17=(1,2)$	$33=(1,3)$	$49=(1,4)$	$65=(1,5)$	$81=(1,6)$	$97=(1,7)$	$113=(1,8)$
$2=(2,1)$	$18=(2,2)$	$34=(2,3)$	$50=(2,4)$	$66=(2,5)$	$82=(2,6)$	$98=(2,7)$	$114=(2,8)$
$3=(3,1)$	$19=(3,2)$	$35=(3,3)$	$51=(3,4)$	$67=(3,5)$	$83=(3,6)$	$99=(3,7)$	$115=(3,8)$
$4=(4,1)$	$20=(4,2)$	$36=(4,3)$	$52=(4,4)$	$68=(4,5)$	$84=(4,6)$	$100=(4,7)$	$116=(4,8)$
$5=(5,1)$	$21=(5,2)$	$37=(5,3)$	$53=(5,4)$	$69=(5,5)$	$85=(5,6)$	$101=(5,7)$	$117=(5,8)$
$6=(6,1)$	$22=(6,2)$	$38=(6,3)$	$54=(6,4)$	$70=(6,5)$	$86=(6,6)$	$102=(6,7)$	$118=(6,8)$
$7=(7,1)$	$23=(7,2)$	$39=(7,3)$	$55=(7,4)$	$71=(7,5)$	$87=(7,6)$	$103=(7,7)$	$119=(7,8)$
$8=(8,1)$	$24=(8,2)$	$40=(8,3)$	$56=(8,4)$	$72=(8,5)$	$88=(8,6)$	$104=(8,7)$	$120=(8,8)$

In this case, we get a **upside-down pandiagonal magic square** of order 32 with magic sum $S_{32 \times 32} := 26666666666640$. It is given below in three parts.

$1=(1,1)$	$17=(1,2)$	$33=(1,3)$	$49=(1,4)$	$65=(1,5)$	$81=(1,6)$	$97=(1,7)$	$113=(1,8)$	$129=(1,9)$
$2=(2,1)$	$18=(2,2)$	$34=(2,3)$	$50=(2,4)$	$66=(2,5)$	$82=(2,6)$	$98=(2,7)$	$114=(2,8)$	$130=(2,9)$
$3=(3,1)$	$19=(3,2)$	$35=(3,3)$	$51=(3,4)$	$67=(3,5)$	$83=(3,6)$	$99=(3,7)$	$115=(3,8)$	$131=(3,9)$
$4=(4,1)$	$20=(4,2)$	$36=(4,3)$	$52=(4,4)$	$68=(4,5)$	$84=(4,6)$	$100=(4,7)$	$116=(4,8)$	$132=(4,9)$
$5=(5,1)$	$21=(5,2)$	$37=(5,3)$	$53=(5,4)$	$69=(5,5)$	$85=(5,6)$	$101=(5,7)$	$117=(5,8)$	$133=(5,9)$
$6=(6,1)$	$22=(6,2)$	$38=(6,3)$	$54=(6,4)$	$70=(6,5)$	$86=(6,6)$	$102=(6,7)$	$118=(6,8)$	$134=(6,9)$
$7=(7,1)$	$23=(7,2)$	$39=(7,3)$	$55=(7,4)$	$71=(7,5)$	$87=(7,6)$	$103=(7,7)$	$119=(7,8)$	$135=(7,9)$
$8=(8,1)$	$24=(8,2)$	$40=(8,3)$	$56=(8,4)$	$72=(8,5)$	$88=(8,6)$	$104=(8,7)$	$120=(8,8)$	$136=(8,9)$
$9=(9,1)$	$25=(9,2)$	$41=(9,3)$	$57=(9,4)$	$73=(9,5)$	$89=(9,6)$	$105=(9,7)$	$121=(9,8)$	$137=(9,9)$

In this case, we get a **upside-down pandiagonal magic square** of order 36 with magic sum $S_{36 \times 36} := 29999999999970$. It is given below in three parts.

1=(1,1)	17=(1,2)	33=(1,3)	49=(1,4)	65=(1,5)	81=(1,6)	97=(1,7)	113=(1,8)	129=(1,9)	145=(1,10)
2=(2,1)	18=(2,2)	34=(2,3)	50=(2,4)	66=(2,5)	82=(2,6)	98=(2,7)	114=(2,8)	130=(2,9)	146=(2,10)
3=(3,1)	19=(3,2)	35=(3,3)	51=(3,4)	67=(3,5)	83=(3,6)	99=(3,7)	115=(3,8)	131=(3,9)	147=(3,10)
4=(4,1)	20=(4,2)	36=(4,3)	52=(4,4)	68=(4,5)	84=(4,6)	100=(4,7)	116=(4,8)	132=(4,9)	148=(4,10)
5=(5,1)	21=(5,2)	37=(5,3)	53=(5,4)	69=(5,5)	85=(5,6)	101=(5,7)	117=(5,8)	133=(5,9)	149=(5,10)
6=(6,1)	22=(6,2)	38=(6,3)	54=(6,4)	70=(6,5)	86=(6,6)	102=(6,7)	118=(6,8)	134=(6,9)	150=(6,10)
7=(7,1)	23=(7,2)	39=(7,3)	55=(7,4)	71=(7,5)	87=(7,6)	103=(7,7)	119=(7,8)	135=(7,9)	151=(7,10)
8=(8,1)	24=(8,2)	40=(8,3)	56=(8,4)	72=(8,5)	88=(8,6)	104=(8,7)	120=(8,8)	136=(8,9)	152=(8,10)
9=(9,1)	25=(9,2)	41=(9,3)	57=(9,4)	73=(9,5)	89=(9,6)	105=(9,7)	121=(9,8)	137=(9,9)	153=(9,10)
10=(10,1)	26=(10,2)	42=(10,3)	58=(10,4)	74=(10,5)	90=(10,6)	106=(10,7)	122=(10,8)	138=(10,9)	154=(10,10)

In this case, we get a **upside-down pandiagonal magic square** of order 40 with magic sum $S_{40 \times 40} := 33333333333300$. It is given below in four parts.

2.15 Upside-down Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 64

Example 15. *Let's consider all the 256 magic squares of order 4 of type 16×16 given in Appendix 5 according to Table 2.1 or Figure 2.1, we have a **upside-down pandiagonal magic square** of order 64 with magic sum $S_{64 \times 64} := 53333333333280$. It is given below in five parts:*

$1=(1,1)$	$11=(1,2)$	$21=(1,3)$	$31=(1,4)$	$41=(1,5)$	$51=(1,6)$	$61=(1,7)$
$2=(2,1)$	$12=(2,2)$	$22=(2,3)$	$32=(2,4)$	$42=(2,5)$	$52=(2,6)$	$62=(2,7)$
$3=(3,1)$	$13=(3,2)$	$23=(3,3)$	$33=(3,4)$	$43=(3,5)$	$53=(3,6)$	$63=(3,7)$
$4=(4,1)$	$14=(4,2)$	$24=(4,3)$	$34=(4,4)$	$44=(4,5)$	$54=(4,6)$	$64=(4,7)$
$5=(5,1)$	$15=(5,2)$	$25=(5,3)$	$35=(5,4)$	$45=(5,5)$	$55=(5,6)$	$65=(5,7)$
$6=(6,1)$	$16=(6,2)$	$26=(6,3)$	$36=(6,4)$	$46=(6,5)$	$56=(6,6)$	$66=(6,7)$
$7=(7,1)$	$17=(7,2)$	$27=(7,3)$	$37=(7,4)$	$47=(7,5)$	$57=(7,6)$	$67=(7,7)$

*In this case, we get a **upside-down magic square** of order 42 with magic sum $S_{42 \times 42} := 349999999999965$. It is given below in three parts.*

3.7 Upside-down Magic Square of Order 48

Example 22. Let's consider 64 magic squares of order 6 of type 8×8 given in Appendix 6 according to Table 1.2 or a part of Figure 3.1 as given below:

1=(1,1)	11=(1,2)	21=(1,3)	31=(1,4)	41=(1,5)	51=(1,6)	61=(1,7)	71=(1,8)
2=(2,1)	12=(2,2)	22=(2,3)	32=(2,4)	42=(2,5)	52=(2,6)	62=(2,7)	72=(2,8)
3=(3,1)	13=(3,2)	23=(3,3)	33=(3,4)	43=(3,5)	53=(3,6)	63=(3,7)	73=(3,8)
4=(4,1)	14=(4,2)	24=(4,3)	34=(4,4)	44=(4,5)	54=(4,6)	64=(4,7)	74=(4,8)
5=(5,1)	15=(5,2)	25=(5,3)	35=(5,4)	45=(5,5)	55=(5,6)	65=(5,7)	75=(5,8)
6=(6,1)	16=(6,2)	26=(6,3)	36=(6,4)	46=(6,5)	56=(6,6)	66=(6,7)	76=(6,8)
7=(7,1)	17=(7,2)	27=(7,3)	37=(7,4)	47=(7,5)	57=(7,6)	67=(7,7)	77=(7,8)
8=(8,1)	18=(8,2)	28=(8,3)	38=(8,4)	48=(8,5)	58=(8,6)	68=(8,7)	78=(8,8)

In this case, we get a *upside-down magic square* of order 48 with magic sum $S_{48 \times 48} := 39999999999960$. It is given below in four parts:

3.9 Upside-down Magic Square of Order 60

Example 24. *Let's consider all the 100 magic squares of order 6 of type 10×10 given in Appendix 6 according to Table 1.2 or Figure 3.1, we have a **upside-down magic square** of order 60 with magic sum $S_{60 \times 60} := 499999999999950$. It is given below in four parts:*

4.5 Upside-down Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 60

Example 29. *Let's consider all the 25 magic squares of order 12 of type 5×5 given in Appendix 7 according to Table 1.3 or as a part of Figure 4.1, we have a **upside-down pandiagonal magic square** of order 12 with magic sum $S_{60 \times 60} := 49999999999950$. It is given below in five parts:*

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